

Female Scholars in Mesopotamia?

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1. Introduction

The scribal system was the primary vehicle for transmitting and preserving knowledge in one of mankind's longest-living traditions of learning—Mesopotamian cuneiform scholarship. Writing and copying literary and scientific compositions was part of education in scribal schools. Modern research distinguishes different levels of scribes. The most learned and experienced of them are defined as scholars. They created literary, religious, and historical works, serialized texts, and other cuneiform compositions, generally described in Assyriology as scholarly or even literary. But neither Sumerian, nor Akkadian has a word equivalent to modern “scientist.” The word for a scribe, *dub-sar/ṭupšarru*, designates a scribe of any professional level including the highest of them—scholars. For instance, the greatest Neo-Assyrian scholar Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, called himself almost only with a modest title “scribe.”² Scholars of the highest qualification were referred to with the term *ummānu*, “the expert.” Thus chief scribes of the kings bore the title *ummānu*. But the same word could also stand for highly qualified artisans, who were not necessarily literate.

A number of ancient disciplines of highest scribal expertise, *ummānūtu*, are known starting with the Old Babylonian period at least.³ These are *bārû*, the haruspex, *āšipu*, the exorcist, *kalû*, the lamentation priest, and *asû*, the physician. The first three were also temple personnel, the so called *ērib bīti*, allowed to enter temple cellas. In the seventh-century Assyria they appear in the lists of court scholars together with a new category—an astronomer/astrologer, *ṭupšar Enūma Anu Enlil*.⁴ The education of Mesopotamian scholars encompassed studying a much wider spectrum of compositions than a basic

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2. May 2018a: 110–112.

3. *Kalû* exists already in the Old Akkadian. Sumerian attestations are, of course, even earlier.

4. E.g., SAA 7 1, see also SAA 10: XIII–XIV.

curriculum.⁵ For obtaining the skills of a scholar a much higher level of proficiency in cuneiform was necessary than for training a scribe, whose duty would be processing economic records. We can add a mathematician and probably an architect⁶ to the list of professions that demanded advanced literacy, numeracy, and the highest level of scribal art. The top level of scribal lore was classified as a secret knowledge of experts and protected by secrecy colophons.⁷ It was conceived as created together with the creation of humankind.⁸

The Sumerian deity of scribes, the goddess Nisaba, is female. The first author known to us by name is the princess and priestess Enheduanna, daughter of Sargon of Agade. Female literacy and numeracy in Mesopotamia, especially in the early periods, is well known, and the existence of female scribes in most periods of Mesopotamian history is beyond any doubt.⁹ Eleanor Robson concluded concerning the scribal education of women: “female scribes learned the standard student exercises, administered large households, and assisted in the maintenance of numerate justice.”¹⁰

2. *Female Scholars*

But were there scholars among literate women? The present study investigates the attestations for female scholarship in Mesopotamia and explores the diachronic changes in this evidence.

Brigitte Lion and Eleanor Robson have identified four texts from the Old Babylonian period with colophons stating that they were written by women. These four texts correlate with the four levels of the scribal education: a syllabary from year 14 of Samsuiluna (1735 BCE), which aimed at basic training in writing signs; two lexical lists of various complexity; and, finally, a literary composition *The Song of the Hoe*, the copying of which required the highest level of not just scribal but scholarly training.¹¹ School texts found in the houses of *nadītus* led to the conclusion that this category of Old Babylonian women was literate;¹² moreover one can assume that they got some training according to standards of scribal schools. Among all the colophons left to us by Mesopotamian scribes only these four Old Babylonian

5. On scribal education, see, e.g., Veldhuis 2014: 204–225, 425–429 and passim, Gesche 2001, particularly pp. 213–219 for the education of scholars.

6. May 2018b. Note that in the first-millennium Babylonia, architects are on the second place (after the scribes themselves) as descendants of scribes, which points out that a builder was a learned profession. This is based on the numbers in Dandamaev 1983: 237, which might have changed due to the recent publications. Despite the very high level of development of mathematics in Mesopotamia and numerous cuneiform mathematical texts there was no world for a mathematician. For the advanced studies of law, see, e.g., Gesche 2001: 217–218, but a “lawyer” was also not categorized in Mesopotamia as a scholarly profession.

7. For means of protecting specialized corpora of professional texts, see Lenzi 2008: 140–215 (with pp. 186–204 on the *Geheimwissen* colophons in particular) and Stevens 2013.

8. Cavigneaux and Jaques 2010.

9. There are a number of studies dedicated to female scribes and authors. E.g., Harris 1990, Lion 2001, 2009, Lion and Robson 2005; Meier 1991; Pearce 1995: 2266; Robson 2007; Stol 2016: 367–371; Westenholz 2006, 1989: 548–549, and Dalley 1984: 110 for Mari, Charpin 2010: 63–64. But note the absence of female scribes in the Neo- and Late Babylonian periods (see below, fn. 70).

10. Robson 2007: 247.

11. Lion and Robson 2005. For Proto á = A, see also Harris 1990: 9.

12. Charpin 2010: 63, with n. 29 on p. 257–258, Wilcke 2000: 32.

texts testify that they were written by women. Not a single first-millennium colophon points to a scholarly text written or copied by a female.

2.1. *Female Diviners, Exorcists, Wailers?*

Two of the aforementioned Akkadian terms for scholars have feminine forms. These are *āšiptu*, literally “woman exorcist,” and *bārītu*, “female diviner.” For both of these professions the female form is attested only once as applied to a mortal woman and not to goddesses. These single attestations stand out in their loneliness against the background of the copious evidence for male representatives of the professions of an exorcist and diviner. The only example for a female exorcist comes from an incantation incorporated into the first-millennium anti-witchcraft ritual *Maqlû*. There the *āšiptu* is listed together with female sorceresses of various types, but also with female cultic personnel.¹³ *Āšiptu* here, together with the other terms in the list, is simply an epithet for a witch who possesses supernatural powers, like the ability to seize “the mouth of the gods,” to bind “the knees of the goddesses,” and to hurt humans. Thus, her evil impact must be neutralized.

Contrarily, female *bāriātu* are mentioned together with *šā'ilātu*, female diviners of the other kind, in an Old Assyrian document. These Old Assyrian she-diviners are asked, alongside the female dream interpreters,¹⁴ to interpret a dream.¹⁵ Significantly, the inquiry comes from a woman as well. The male *šā'ilu*, the oneiromancer, is usually attested beside a male *bārû* and seems to be, according to CAD, “a popular rather than a professional diviner.”¹⁶ However, for a male *šā'ilu* CAD suggests a concrete professional specialization “dream interpreter, necromancer.”¹⁷ In my eyes it is not the degree of “professionalism” but the relation to the written tradition and the kind of specialisation that matters here. Neither a male *šā'ilu* nor a female *šā'iltu* are known as authors or copyists of any divinatory text. It might be because in order to perform a divination the *bārû* was to examine the intestines of a sacrificial animal. Thus from the earliest periods he was closely connected with the temple,¹⁸ which was a stronghold of the Mesopotamian scholarly tradition.

Kalû, Sumerian gala, the lamentation priest, who often performed a female role, was a profession with “unique gender identity.”¹⁹ The Sumerian *kalû*'s laments are written in Emesal. Although Emesal was a “women's language,”²⁰ the sex of *kalû*-priests was doubtlessly male. Female mourners, ama-gal, are known from Ur III texts, where they are closely associated with the male gala/*kalû*.²¹ A document

13. *Kaššāptu nērtānītu elēnītu naršimdatu āšiptu eššebūtu mušlahḫatu agugiltu qadištu nadītu ištarītu kulmašītu*, “Witch, murderess, denouncer, *naršimdatu*, exorcist, ecstatic, snake charmer, *agugiltu*, *qadištu*-votary, *nadītu*-woman, Ištar-votary, *kulmašītu*-votary” (*Maqlû* III 39–44 = AMD 10: 87–88, 242, 307).

14. Harris 1990: 12.

15. *annakam šā'ilātīm bārī' ātim' u eṭemṁē nušālma*, “we are inquiring here of women dream interpreters, women diviners, and the spirits of the dead” (TCL 4 5: 5).

16. See CAD Š I 110b and Harris 1990: 13.

17. CAD Š I 110b–112a.

18. See May 2017 with further literature.

19. Gabbay 2008: 4–56.

20. A. Löhnert (2008: 423) suggested to define Emesal as a sociolect. But G. Rubio (2009, especially p. 32) has shown that it is actually a genrelect. For the interpretation of Emesal as a “thin language,” see Michalowski 2004: 23.

21. As are also three more female cultic professions: ama-ér-ra, dam-ab-ba, and um-ma (idem: 2011: 68, 70).

from Garšana²² testifies that *ér* (= *takribtum*) laments were performed by gala lamentation priests together with *ama-gal* female mourners.²³ Twice the Old Babylonian literary compositions are defined as *amirakutum*: firstly, they are designated as *ama-ér-ra-ku-tim ša DINGIR.MAḤ*, i.e., Bēlet-ilī, in the colophon of the tablet-basket label,²⁴ and secondly, the unpublished hymn to Mama/Bēlet-ilī is called in the catch-line of its colophon *a-mi-ra-ku-tum*.²⁵ Their headings demonstrate the relationship of these compositions to *ama'errû*. But the Akkadian word *ama'errû*, “female mourner,” “wailing woman,” derived from the Sumerian *ama-ér-ra* is extremely rare and only known from lexical lists. Furthermore, there is nothing that points to the female authorship of the aforementioned laments or hymn.²⁶

2.2. Female Physicians

Nonetheless, one of the scholarly professions was mastered by women starting with its very first occurrence in the Early Dynastic period (ca. 2500 BCE). This is the profession of a physician. We do not know the Akkadian word for it. In both Akkadian and Sumerian texts it is written ideographically as *a-zu munus* or *munus a-zu*, where *a-zu* is “physician” and *munus* a “female” determinative. Again, the main Mesopotamian healing deities were always female.²⁷ These are the Sumerian goddesses Nintiguda, Ninkarrak and Ninisina, who by the second millennium merge into one goddess—Gula.²⁸ Gula was one of the most important deities of the pantheon. Gula, *azugallatu*, “the great physician,” was also a female sage, *apkallatu*.²⁹ In the Gula Hymn by Bulliṣa-rabi, among her other wisdom qualities she is assigned with the professions of an exorcist, *āšiptu*, and a diviner, *bārītu*.³⁰

Probably the first mortal female physician, whose sex is suggested by her possibly female name, appears after the priest of Gula in a list of witnesses on a field-sales deed from Šuruppak dated to the Fara period.³¹ A female physician *Du-bil-da-mu a-zu munus* from a place called Ada is attested twice in a text from Ebla.³² Her name and title are found in a long account of persons who receive textiles.

Best documented is the female physician Ubartum. Almost fifty texts from the Ur III period contain her name, but she is designated as a physician in only seven of them. However, all these are economic

22. CUSAS 3 1035.

23. Gabbay 2011: 71.

24. Shaffer 1993: 209; BM 85563: 10–12 mentions 37(!) landscape tablets of this genre.

25. Groneberg 2003: 56, 59.

26. CAD AII 1a.

27. Two sons of Gula/Ninkarrak, Damu and Ninazu, are to the best of my knowledge the only Mesopotamian male healing gods. Despite his name, the healing functions of Ninazu are overshadowed by his functions as the city god of Enegi and Ešnunna. He is primarily a chthonic deity, who in the medical texts is found only in the incantations against a snake bite. The cults of both brothers disappear after the Old Babylonian period.

28. On the syncretism of the healing goddesses see, e.g., in Asher-Greve and Westenholz 2013: 82–86.

29. The term *apkallatu* and its main masculine form *apkallu* is applied respectively to Gula and to males exclusively (Harris 1990: 4). Gula is called *apkallat ilāni*, “the wise (woman) of the gods” in STT 73:2 3 (Reiner 1960: 32), and *apkallat barāt muššipat kalama*, “a wise (woman), a diviner (woman), an exorcist (woman) of all” in K. 232: 29 (Mullo-Weir 1929: 17).

30. Lambert 1967: 128, line 183 of The Gula Hymn of Bulliṣa-rabi. R. Harris (1990: 3, n. 1) stresses that in this very composition “the traditional roles of women” as a daughter, daughter-in-law, spouse and housekeeper “are best summed.”

31. See Krecher 1973: 196 no. 1 v 9–10. The element *nin* in this early period does not necessarily indicate a female and *a-zu* appears, as is the way of this period, without a determinative. A female witness is unusual. Cf. Kleinermann 2011: 179, n. 16.

32. ARET 1, no. 1 rev. v 3–4; x 12–13.

documents that cover a sixteen-year period. We do not have at our disposal any text written by Ubartum herself. Ubartum belonged to a very prominent Garšana family. Both of her brothers also bore the title “physician.” Moreover, one of them was a general and the governor of Garšana, married to a princess, daughter of Šulgi.³³ Thus, the doctor in the Ur III period was an honourable profession and even statesmen could hold it. It has been suggested that Ubartum was actually a gynaecologist but no evidence points to this.³⁴

There are several attestations for female physicians in the Old Babylonian period: a female physician is mentioned in a grain distribution list on the 21st of the month Simānu of year 51 of Rīm-Sîn,³⁵ munus a-zu appears as entry 705 in the Old Babylonian lexical list lú from Nippur,³⁶ a female doctor is attested in two letters found at Mari.³⁷

Interesting in this context is an Old Babylonian birth incantation known in four copies:³⁸ one bilingual (AUAM 73.3094) and the remaining three Sumerian. One of the latter is dated to the 35th year of Ammi-ditana (1648 BCE,³⁹ BM 97093) and the other to the year 7 of Samsuiluna (1742 BCE, MLC 1207). In three of the four copies of this incantation, Sumerian is distinctly remarkable by its orthography. To one extent or another these three copies are all written in syllabic Sumerian and in fact present a phonetic transcription that, by and large, ignores conventional Sumerian orthography. Sumerian logograms designating the roots and grammatical elements are rendered phonetically and only the pronunciation of the words of the language, which by the time of the composition of this text was no longer spoken, is transmitted. In E 47.190 and AUAM 73.3094 the determinatives are written only with the divine names.⁴⁰ It is clear that the purpose of phonetic writing was to help a performer pronouncing an orally recited incantation. Most of the texts, for which the same phenomenon of syllabic Sumerian is attested, are compositions written in Emesal.⁴¹ This served the purpose of oral recitation by lamentation priests.⁴² The overwhelming majority of the Old Babylonian syllabic texts written in Emegir, the main dialect of Sumerian, come either from provinces, or from the areas where Sumerian was never a spoken language, or even from the lands where even Akkadian was foreign.⁴³ Some of them also belong to the

33. Kleinermann 2011: 179–180.

34. Eadem: 179, with n. 18.

35. AO 8493: 27, published as TCL 10 107 and edited in Jean 1931: no. 114, with the reading munus a-zu[?] marked as questionable. A collation by the present author proved that an Old Babylonian variant of the sign ZU appears on this tablet and thus the reading munus a-zu is certain.

36. Edited by J. Taylor: <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/dcclt/corpus> (visited on 16.09.2017).

37. ARM 10 18: 3; ARM 10 72:14–15; Dalley 1984: 110, Harris 1990: 11.

38. Those are BM 97093 (unpublished); E 47.190 (Farber 1984); MLC 1207 (van Dijk 1975); AUAM 73.3094 (Cohen 1976). Few lines in Akkadian and the colophon, which dates this text to the reign of Ammiditana, are preserved on the reverse of BM 97093. E 47.190 rev. 6', 8', contains rubrics in Akkadian (Farber 1984: 314).

39. According to the middle chronology.

40. On the one hand, this can be the evidence that the word dingir was in fact pronounced, but on the other it can be just a matter of reverence.

41. Kercher 1967, especially pp. 25–28.

42. Delnero 2015.

43. Krecher 1967: 28–30. The known locations include Šaduppûm, Mari, Assur, and Huzirîna, but also Susa, Ugarit, and Hatušša. Very few texts come from Girsu (Tello) and Sippar, and only one from Kiš and one from Nippur.

repertory of lamentation priests. Paul Delnero has shown that syllabic rendering in case of lamentations was by no means caused by the scribe's ignorance, but only by the necessities of oral performance.⁴⁴ I suggest that this was primarily the need to memorize the text of the birth incantation in order to recite or sing it, which was realized by its orthographic writing in the three copies. However, given that we know of the existence of female doctors in the Old Babylonian period and before, and that this is an obstetrical text, it is tempting to suggest that it was probably written by and/or for a female physician, who was literate and had to know to chant an incantation as a part of the her medical treatment.

2.3. Female Herbalists

Another female profession was closely associated with medicine.⁴⁵ It is *muraqqītu*, ideographically written as ^mĪ.RÁ.RÁ, literally meaning “the one who mixes the oils.” Notably, two translations were suggested for this word in the same issue of *Archiv für Orientforschungen*. Ernst Weidner believed it is an “Apotheker.”⁴⁶ However, Benno Landsberger in the same volume stresses that “‘Parfümeur’ (nicht ‘Apotheker’)”⁴⁷ is the meaning of *muraqqû*. His opinion naturally is expressed in the Chicago Assyrian Dictionary which translates this word as a “perfume maker.” Wolfram von Soden, however, kept the neutral “Salbenmischerin” for *muraqqītu*, though his Akkadisches Handwörterbuch translates *muraqqû*, the masculine form of the term for the same profession, as “Parfümeur.”⁴⁸ The Akkadian word *muraqqû* is of Assyrian origin and is attested already in an Old Assyrian letter.⁴⁹ The use of the term continues into the Middle Assyrian and Neo-Assyrian dialects. Under Assyrian influence the traditional Babylonian *raqqû* is replaced by the Assyrian *muraqqītu*. In the Old Akkadian and Old Babylonian periods, including Mari, *raqqû*⁵⁰ designates the same profession as the Assyrian *muraqqû* in Neo-Babylonian texts. For the latter the ideogram Ī.RÁ.RÁ literally meaning “oils mixer” is used, but for *raqqû* also ŠIM.SAR/MÚ is found.⁵¹ The latter can be interpreted as a “herbalist.”⁵² The feminine form of the word is not attested in Akkadian at all in any period, but the Early Dynastic texts from Šuruppak dealing with the allocation of barley have dam šim-mú, which apparently means she-herbalist; moreover in Lagash of the Early Dynastic III

44. Delnero 2015: 115.

45. Herbs were widely used in Mesopotamia by exorcists, whose primary function was healing, and by physicians. Furthermore, in *A Dog for Nintinuga*, a literary composition unearthed in a scribal school at Nippur, šim-mú, the herbalist, appears among the epithets of this healing goddess after a-zu, the physician (a-zu sag₉-ge šim-mú tur₅-ra-ta, physician, herbalist of the sick” (UM 29-16-139+ rev. iii 28, see <http://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/etcsl.cgi?text=c.5.7.2#> accessed on 23.02.2018).

46. Weidner 1935–1936: 17.

47. Landsberger 1935–1936: 150.

48. CAD M II 218a and AHW 675b s.v. *muraqqītu* and *muraqqiu* / *muraqqû* respectively.

49. KAV 194: 9.

50. For Mari, see Cousin 2016: 513–514 with further references. For *bīt raqqīm*, see Joannès 1993: 262. For the Old Babylonian Larsa—Middeke-Conlin 2014: 15. R. Middeke-Conlin (2014) analysed the evidence for the production of aromatics in Larsa of the Old Babylonian period. H. Brunke and W. Sallaberger (2010) discuss perfume recipes of the Ur III period and the evidence for the use of perfumes, (ibid.: 53) in the Old Sumerian period.

51. Lexical sections in CAD M II 218 s.v. *muraqqû* and R174 s.v. *raqqû* respectively and Canonical lú = ša (MSL XII: 137, ll. 257, 259). For the Old Babylonian Larsa, see Middeke-Conlin 2014: 15–16, who translates *raqqû* as “perfumer,” but discusses the ambiguity of the term.

52. Cf. Middeke-Conlin 2014: 16.

period aromatic oils, their acquisition, production, and distribution, were associated with the household of the ruler's wife (é-mí) which was also the household of the healing goddess Bau (é-ba-ba₆).⁵³ Contrarily to *raqqû*, Assyrian *muraqqîtu* was a predominantly female profession. Apart from lexical lists, masculine *muraqqû* is only attested three times, while for women this profession is widely represented both in Middle and Neo-Assyrian texts. The “oil mixer” might encompass both professions, that of a perfume maker and of an apothecary. Moreover, there is a substantial overlapping between perfume recipes and medical recipes, written by physicians and exorcists.⁵⁴ I suggest to interpret *muraqqû/muraqqîtu* as a “herbalist,” which reflects well the functions of this profession, its relationship to Mesopotamian medicine and place in healing practices.⁵⁵

The majority of the Middle Assyrian textual evidence for perfume makers comes from the archive of the Middle Assyrian high official Bābu-aḥa-iddina. His household was a centre of perfume production apparently for the needs of the palace.⁵⁶ Here we find also the term *rab muraqqiāte*, “the head of the female oil mixers.”

In the Neo-Assyrian period the profession of an oil mixer still exists and is connected to the palace as well. Thus a *muraqqîtu* together with her two maids appears in the list of female personnel.⁵⁷ In the Neo-Babylonian period, six *muraqqêtu* are mentioned in a list of oil distribution dated to the 13th year of Nebuchadnezzar II together with the exiled Judean king Jehoiachin, his five sons, and other exiled Judeans. The herbalists, *muraqqêtu*, are listed in two other oil distribution texts among various exiles that received goods at the royal court.⁵⁸

The only instances where female perfume mixers are mentioned in scholarly texts derive from the Middle Assyrian period. These are two colophons of perfume recipes. The better preserved of the two dates to the fifth regnal year of Tukulti-Ninurta I (conventionally 1240 BCE) and reads as follows (KAR 220 = VAT 10165 = N 1 [34]):⁵⁹

Rev. col. iv
 8' r̄tār¹²-qi²¹-tu ša 2 BĀN ḫ^{mes} giš GI e-li-e DÙG.GA šá UGU LUGAL
 9' i-r̄na¹ pi-i mi^rTap-pu-ti-d^dNIN-É.GAL-lim mi^(SAL)mu-raq(SAL)-qi-te⁶⁰ na-ás-ḥa

53. For the editions of the Šuruppak texts, see Pomponio and Visicato 1994: no. 6 rev. iii 10–11 (p. 60) and no. 10 i 5–7 (p. 71); the discussion of the meaning of šim-sar/mú, *ibid.*: 62, n. 15; for the ED III Lagash texts, see Selz 1989: 528–531 (Nik 300–301) and DP 222 (CDLI no. P220872). For the é-mí and é-ba-ba₆ as the same institution, see Maekawa 1973–1974: 81–81, 140. It is worth noting, however, that in TSA 6 the fragrances for production of aromatic oils are supplied by the household of the ruler(!) to his servant. I am most grateful to Professor G. Selz for providing me this information.

54. Ebeling 1950.

55. Cf. Dalley 1984: 122, for the use of plants by Mesopotamian healers of both sex. See also Charpin 2017: 52–59, who pointed out that the name of the temple of Gula at Larsa was é-ú-nam-ti-l-1a, “the house of the herb of life;” see also his observation on p. 53 with the reference to RIME 11: 1–4.

56. Jakob 2003: 476–486.

57. SAA 7 24 rev. 8–9.

58. Babylon 28122 I 9, ii 11 and Babylon 28186 = VAT 16378: 5, Babylon 28232: 6. See Weidner 1939: 924–928, and pls. I-II, IV, V; Jursa 2010: 72.

59. Jakob 2003: 482–483. For the archival context of this text, see Pedersén 1986: 18, 21 (N 1 [34]).

60. Such writing of *muraqqîtu* points to a sign play by the scribe.

10'^{iti} *Mu-ḥur*–DINGIR^{meš} UD 20^{kám} *li-mu* ^mŠu-nu–qar-du GAL KAŠ.LUL

8' *Oil preparation for 2 sūt of pure (and) fine cane oil for the king.*

9' Excerpted *according to the mouth* of Tappūti-bēlat-ekalli, the female oil mixer;

10' month *Muḥur-ilāni*, the 20th day; the eponymate of Šunu-qardū, the chief cupbearer.

The expression *i-na pi-i*, “according to the mouth” in this colophon is commonly interpreted in favour of a scribe writing down the recipe dictated by Tappūti-bēlat-ekalli.⁶¹ This might be correct, but it should be stressed that the phrase (*ana*) *pī ummāni*⁶²/*apkalle*⁶³ in the colophons does not necessarily designate that the text was dictated by a headmaster. To the contrary, both K. 4023 and KAR 177 relate the creation of the original of the copied text to the antediluvian sages, who by no means could dictate its content to the copyist. K. 4023: 22 even states that these were the sages “from before the flood.” Much more often the term *pī tuppī* designates that the tablet was copied from another tablet, most often from an ancient original.⁶⁴ Clearly the use of this expression in KAR 220: 9' indicates the process of keeping and transmitting scholarly tradition. It is worth noting that the anonymous scribe did not put his name on the colophon of KAR 220.

Only a part of a single but long line of the colophon of another perfume recipe, VAT 9659, is preserved (rev. 31).⁶⁵ It also contains a reference to a female herbalist: [...]-*ni-nu*[?] *mu-ra-qi-te na-ās-ḥa-TA*[?]. The last word must be normalised as the feminine stative *nashat*,⁶⁶ which is the only attestation of this form for this verb. It can refer to the female scribe of this tablet and in this case must be translated as: “...(of) PN, the female perfume-maker, (she) excerpted.” The alternative is that *nashat* refers to [*tuppu*], “tablet,”

61. Although note that Hunger (1968: 11, 33) translates it as “Auf Befehl... ”

62. So BE 8 133: 9 and UM 1/2, 106 rev. 30. The latter does not provide the scribe’s name and even states that the scribe did not see the original. That may imply that the headmaster dictated the text reading it from the tablet. In NBS 7832: 37 the same formula is partly preserved as well (Goetze 1950: 74). See Hunger 1968: 8 for a short discussion, where he points to the expression *ša pī ummāni šatir* as sometimes written at the bottom of the tablets of the series *Enūma Anu Enlil*. For presumably oral scholarly explanations and examinations(?), similarly described in the colophons and incipits of commentaries, see Frahm 2011: 51–56. However, N. Veldhuis stresses that “What that means for the practice of composing or utilizing such texts remains a matter of speculation” (Veldhuis 2014: 403). Further, for the oral tradition as a source of commentaries, see Frahm 2011: 86–87.

63. Thus the colophon of the medical text K. 4023: 22 (Lambert 1957: 8). M. Lambert compared it to the colophon of KAR 177 iv 25, where he restored *a[p[?]-kal[?]-li[?]]*. However, A. Livingstone, who treated this text most recently reads *u[m-ma-n-n]* there (CUSAS 25: 179).

64. Cf. Hunger 1968: 171, s.v. *pū*.

65. The complete height of this tablet was ca. 25 cm, the width—ca. 17 cm. The surviving length of the colophon line is ca. 6.5 cm—slightly more than one third of its original length.

The tablet has a typical Middle Assyrian appearance: red core, white slip, which is almost completely worn on the obverse, and “firing holes.” Its maximal preserved thickness is ca. 4.5 cm. Each of the tablet’s sides contained a single column. 10.7 cm of the height on the reverse are left uninscribed, except for the single line of the colophon below the ruling.

66. TA stands for *-at*. This is a mirror writing (Deller 1962: 192; Cohen and Llop: 109) or an “überhängender Vokal.” I would like to express my gratitude to J. Llop for discussing this phenomenon of the Middle Assyrian texts with me.

which is by and large feminine in Middle Assyrian, but it is noticeably rarely feminine in colophons.⁶⁷ The writing of *muraqqītu* in VAT 9659 rev. 31 is not as elaborated as it is in KAR 220: 9'. It is neither preceded by a female determinative, nor contains any sign plays. The signs of VAT 9659 are quite large—4.5–5 mm as opposed to 2.5–3 mm in KAR 220. But nonetheless, if the former interpretation is correct, this is the only known Middle Assyrian scholarly text written by a woman. If so, this text, which is the recipe of an herbal ointment, was excerpted by a female herbalist. Then it is also the latest cuneiform scholarly text known to be written by a woman.⁶⁸ Remarkably, both “perfume recipes,” KAR 220 and VAT 9659, derive from the library of the Aššur temple.

3. Conclusion

To sum up, in the early periods our knowledge about women mastering scholarly professions is obscured by the commonly lacking determinatives designating the gender of professionals. In the first millennium, when these determinatives were regularly written, we do not have any evidence for female scholars either in Assyria or in Babylonia. Evidence for female scholarship disappears on the backdrop of a visible rise in longing to protect textual corpora serving increasingly growing scholarly specialisation.⁶⁹ But it should be stressed that in the first-millennium high ranking women also are much less visible than in the early periods and the absence of female scholars might result from the decline of social status of women towards the end of Mesopotamian history.⁷⁰ This is correct also for the divine realm. Thus, in the first millennium male Nabû is found as the divinity of scribal art much more frequently than female Nisaba. Nonetheless, it cannot be assumed that female scholars did not exist in the third and second millennia. Contrarily, female doctors certainly existed. The evidence assembled by Lion and Robson about the curriculum texts copied by women in the Old Babylonian period challenges the assumption of Rivka Harris that there is no evidence that girls ever attended schools.⁷¹ But except for these four instances all the evidence of women in scholarly professions in Mesopotamia is limited to female physicians and herbalists. It has been often suggested that the female physicians served other women, like *nadītus*⁷² or *šakintus*,⁷³ or even “functioned to curtail access of male non-kin to women of the harem.”⁷⁴ Harris also assumed that in Mesopotamia female physician functioned as “modern gynaecologist,

67. Cf. *šaṭrat* in KAR 16 rev. 30' and KAR 15 rev. 16' edited in Wagensohn 2008: 284, which might imply feminine for *tuppu* in these MA colophons. However, KAR 16 rev. 29' has masculine *tup-pi ša-ṭa-ri*. Hunger 1968: nos. 158, 291, 296, 328, 470 and 498 have clearly masculine *tuppu* versus a single OB attestation of feminine in no. 15.

68. Cf. transliteration and translation in Ebeling 1950: 41–46: for his handcopy, see plates 6–8. For the archival context, see Pedersén 1985: 37, 39; (M2 [21]). For the active stative, see Huenehergard 1987: 228–229.

69. See Borger 1957–1971, Lenzi 2008: 170–225, Stevens 2013.

70. R. Harris (1990: 8) pointed out that in all the bulk of the first millennium Babylonian texts there is not a single mention of a female scribe either. Her assumption goes back to the work of Dandamaev. But recently C. Wunsch confirmed to me that she has never run into a Neo- or Late Babylonian female scribe. Thus Harris' observation is still correct.

71. Harris 1990:15.

72. E.g., Stol 2016: 595.

73. Svärd 2015: 91–105.

74. Dalley 1984: 122, Harris 1990: 11 about female physician at Mari (ARM 10 72: 14–15).

obstetrician, paediatrician”.⁷⁵ Marten Stol states, following Nele Ziegler, that female doctors “Undoubtedly ... were occupied solely with the care of women, and as such can be considered the world’s first recorded gynaecologists.”⁷⁶ It might well be that for female doctors the first priority was the care of women, although in many early and traditional societies healers acting as “general practitioners” are female.⁷⁷ But there are no indications that the expertise of a female Mesopotamian physician was ever limited to the female or infant body.⁷⁸ Moreover, contrarily to Stol’s statement, there is not a single textual record testifying that female physicians specialized in gynaecology or that gynaecology was a medical specialisation of women only. More important is that the evidence for female scholarship in general and for female doctors in particular is incomparably scarcer than the evidence about male scholarship. Unlike male scholarship the female one was not institutionalized, since even male physicians are not attested holding prebends and positions in temples⁷⁹ as did the representatives of the other three traditional scholarly professions. Finally, in the third–beginning of the second-millennium female practitioners are called “doctors,” similarly to male physicians, but starting with the middle of the second millennium on their role is limited to that of a herbalist at best. Moreover, the aforementioned passage in the anti-witchcraft ritual, where the female “exorcist” *āšiptu* is listed among sorcerers, clearly brands her as a witch, similar to what happened in the Middle Ages.⁸⁰ Growing institutionalisation of scholarship toward the end of Mesopotamian history led to complete expulsion of women from this realm, at least on the level of temple officialdom and textual record.

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75. Harris 1990: 12.

76. Stol 2016: 371 writes about the aforementioned Mari female physicians and refers to Ziegler 1999: 29. E. Robson (2008: 473) points to the almost complete absence of information concerning medical treatment of royal women in the correspondence of the Neo-Assyrian kings: “We should probably thus infer ... women’s domain of healing and midwifery in the royal palace, whose practitioners did not report to the king—or at least did not do so through correspondence in cuneiform.”

77. Cf. Green 1989 on the Middle Ages with further references to broader literature.

78. Cf. Green 1989, where she brilliantly rebukes such approach to mediaeval female caretakers and demonstrates that neither “women’s health was women’s business,” nor that female practitioners’ knowledge was limited to women’s and children’s diseases.

79. For the possibility that at least in Assyria male physicians could be priests of the healing goddess Bābu, see May 2017 and May 2018c. For an *asû* associated with the temple of Gula at Nippur in the Kassite period, see Sassmannshausen (2001: 73 with n. 1173 and further literature). Other evidence for the priests of Gula as healers comes from the Neo-Babylonian copy (818 BCE) of a literary composition, a comic tale originally no later than the Kassite period (George 1993: 65). There the priest of Gula at Isin, the main cultic centre of this healing goddess, cures a patient who has been bitten by a dog (IM 78552: 5, *ibid.*: 66–67). A. George is confident that this priest was an *asû* (*ibid.*: 72).

80. *Maqlû* III 39–44, fn. 13, cf. Green 1989: 449–452.

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